

CONSIDERATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE STUDENTS STUDYING GUIDE GUIDE AND TRANSLATION ACTIVITY AND THE ACHIEVEMENTS ACHIEVED IN THIS FIELD.

Usmanova Sayyora Norimkulovna

Teacher of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

ABSTRACT This article describe the role of the guide in the "organization of the tour service", its qualities, the specifics of the profession of guide and what features it should have.

Keywords: Guide accompaniment, excursionist, communicability, organization, constructiveness, oratory, external speech, internal speech.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in our country, great importance is attached to the rapid development of the tourism sector, and in the medium-term perspective, the implementation of the domestic tourism development program "Travel through the territories of the Republic" has been set. The fulfillment of these tasks requires the further development of tourism and excursion services in Uzbekistan. Tourism excursion service is one of the main services in the field of tourism. Any tourist who visits first of all wants to get acquainted with the country's history, culture, social life, and natural resources. has an effect.

METHODOLOGY

The tasks facing the tour service can be shown as follows;

Guiding was not considered a profession until recently, it was just a fun activity for a group of amateurs. The work of the guide was carried out by specialists of various fields without separating from their main activities (pedagogues, scientific staff of the museum, scientific staff of the institute, etc.). Only a few sightseeing

establishments and individual museums had guides in the state. But at that time, this activity began to have professional characteristics."

The change in the function of the excursion service, its transformation from the form of recreation to the organizational form of cultural and educational work in labor communities, to the network serving the population, led to the rise of a new specialty, that is, the role of a guide.

Article 3 of the Law on Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes the concepts of tourist group leader (tour leader) and guide (excursion leader). A person acting on his behalf and ensuring the fulfillment of the terms of the tourist service contract ", "Guide (ekakursuya leader) - provides excursion-informational, organizational services and qualified assistance to tour participants within the framework of the tourist services contract. Definitions of "indicating natural person" are included.

It is necessary for every guide to know not only the knowledge of his specialty, but also the basics of pedagogy and psychology. It is necessary to be demanding.

The guide's communication with the excursionists, his recommendations and instructions have an educational effect. The information being studied enriches their consciousness spiritually and aesthetically. It educates, forms a worldview. As in all pedagogical processes, two parties are involved in the excursion service: the teacher-guide and the student excursionist. The guide gives knowledge on a certain topic, and the excursionists receive it. The interaction between these two parties is the basis of the pedagogical process. In interaction with the tourists, the guide uses methods of pedagogical influence.

Pedagogical skills and pedagogical art form part of the professional qualification of a guide. Pedagogical skills of the guide include the following: - sufficient knowledge of the specialty; - ability to analyze, imaginative thinking; - understanding the psyche of the excursionist; - being able to manage a group; - to acquire knowledge and skills in the field of pedagogical techniques; - intuition; - respecting the tourist's personality.

The profession of a guide requires specific practical skills. This qualification gives him the ability to correctly select, embody and effectively transfer his knowledge to the audience.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

During the excursion, the guide should ensure that the excursionists think together, analyze, sympathize, unite according to their interests and become a team. The guide should pay attention not only to educational, but also educational aspects of the excursion service. He should choose and use excursion information in such a way that excursionists develop such qualities as love for the homeland, respect for other nations, and their traditions.

In addition to choosing and providing complete and accurate information about the objects, the guide must also have personal qualities and professional skills. Ethical requirements imposed on a person are compliance with general principles and moral norms, striving for perfection. The formation of a person to be perfect and perfect in all aspects takes place during his whole life (in a general education school, college, higher education institution, in the community, in everyday life, in training courses for guides, in interaction with excursionists).

The main activity of the guide is to prepare and conduct the excursion service [5].

Preparation of excursion service is divided into 3 parts:

- 1) Preparation of individual text;
- 2) Remembering the requirements of methodical development;
- 3) Remembering the route.

The guide must develop and improve the following 4 types of abilities in order to be able to attract the tourists during the excursion, to maintain a stable group atmosphere:

- Constructivity;
- Organization;
- Communicativeness;

-Analysis.

Constructive ability is expressed in the ability to correctly select and formalize the information of the excursion service for the tourists, to convey it in an understandable and reliable way, to revise the excursion plan and the method of using methodological guides in necessary cases, and the guide's thinking is the basis of ability.

Organizational ability is reflected in the ability to manage the excursion group, direct their attention to the desired object, and perform services in the approved program for tourists and excursionists.

Communicative ability to establish a warm relationship when working with the excursion group, to maintain this atmosphere during the excursion service, to be able to absorb the characteristic of the culture of behavior and during the route, the bus driver, exhibition, museum workers, heads of methodological circles, is manifested in the process of establishing a proper relationship with other guides, leaders of tourist groups.

The ability to analyze is manifested in a critical analysis of one's work, an objective assessment of the quality of the excursion service, and the effectiveness of the application of methodological methods.

The role of the guide's temperament is important in the organization of the excursion service. Manifestation of human temperament (sanguine, choleric, melancholic, phlegmatic) is the result of general human culture. The guide's character, world view, free thinking, relationship established with the team qualitatively determines how the tour will go. The guide should know the norm in showing his inner and outer feelings and attitudes to the tourists.

"The guide's emotions, mood (extremely high or depressed) arising under the influence of external and internal disturbances should not affect the excursion process, self-control, providing the necessary environment in the group is the skill of the guide. the guide's feelings must have an objective character."

Each person has his own characteristics (speech, conveyance of information, gestures) that distinguish him from others. The guide should have the ability to speak fluently, to attract tourists, and to convey information to tourists correctly and clearly. Visual delivery of any historical stories, legends, myths is the main feature of the guide. The guide should learn the culture of speech, manners and be able to demonstrate it during the excursion. Because speech culture and manners are the main criteria that determine the general morality of a person. "Speech culture" means conveying the messages that need to be said, respecting the listener, with literary expressions suitable for him.

The concept of "speech" refers to oral and written speech. Both of them will be meaningful, understandable, expressive and modern. Guide's culture of written speech can be seen when working with the following documents: main and individual texts, methodical manuals, abstracts, lectures, reviews, bibliographic images. The main text is written in literary language, and the individual text is written in more spoken language. Speech is divided into external and internal speech. External speech has communicative importance, and its essence is aimed at hearing and understanding of other people. "Establishing contact of a single speaker with many listeners is a relatively complex communicative process". .

Inner speech is the speech of a person's inner world, the pre-formation of thoughts that should be conveyed to the audience. A person has a dialogue with his inner voice thinking about a subject. He thinks with the help of his internal speech, in which he uses auxiliary tools such as drawings, images, tables. When we talk about the public speaking audience, the audience can be complex and very complex. Therefore, when a speaker (guide) goes to a large audience, he must prepare seriously, be ready for any situation and questions. [4]

Guide requirements

The appearance of the guide should include the following:

- compliance with personal hygiene;
- neat appearance;

- discipline in actions;
- cultured dress;
- he should not smoke while working.

In turn, such features leave a warm impression on tourists. It should also have personal qualities. For example,

- good physical health;
- mental stability;
- to be accessible;
- order should be disciplined;
- to be polite;
- should have artistic ability and be able to be a director and organizer. Because the guide is not only a representative of the travel agency, but also his country is a person who advertises his potential, gives new information to the guests and helps them to perform certain actions. The most important thing is that the guide should be able to provide 1st medical aid in case of an accident.

CONCLUSION

Development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, training of all personnel and specialists in this field, welcoming visitors in accordance with all standards and providing them with high-quality services, being able to show the history, culture, traditions of our country accompanied by a guide, and tourists gaining interest is one of the important tasks. Therefore, the field of tour guides serves as an advertiser of the tourist potential of our country and an attractor of tourists.

Reference

I.S.Tuxliyev ; R.S.Amriddinova; G.R.Tursunova."Ekskursiya xizmatini tashkil qilish"// O'quv qo'llanma

T: "Barkamol fayz media", 2018, 296 bet// 32,36,38- betlar.

Емельянов.Б.В. "Экскурсоведение" Уч.пос. М. 2006 //117 с

Abduqasimovna, A. S. (2022). DIFFERENT VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS AND PEDAGOGUES-SCIENTISTS ABOUT THE CHILD AND HIS EDUCATION. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(5), 348-352.

Abduqasimovna, A. S. (2022). ATTENTION TO THE EDUCATION OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE AND REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(5), 342-347.

Абдумажитова, С. А. (2019). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ ЧУВСТВА ВРЕМЕНИ КАК ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОГО ФЕНОМЕНА В ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ И МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (3), 81-83.

Abduqasimovna, A. S. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6508403>. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(1), 265-269.